

EARTHONE UPDATE | Summer 26

EARTHONE General Assembly

In May 2026, the EARTHONE consortium met in Padova, Italy, for the project's 4th General Assembly. Partners reviewed progress across pilot sites, tested digital tools and discussed ongoing work on soil monitoring, climate modelling and stakeholder engagement. The meeting also included a visit to the Italian pilot site in the Veneto region, connecting technical discussions with field realities and agricultural practice.

[Full story](#)

Upcoming webinar

World Day to Combat Desertification and Drought

EARTHONE is co-organising a webinar through the [AgroTechHub Cluster](#) focused on soil degradation, desertification and resilient land systems.

 17 June 2026

 11:00 CEST

The session will bring together Horizon Europe projects and experts working on soil restoration, climate resilience and sustainable land management.

[Register now](#)

Practice abstracts available

EARTHONE has published its first Practice Abstracts, presenting project knowledge and activities in a concise format accessible to practitioners, stakeholders and policymakers.

Click on each image below to view the corresponding document.

#1

Climate-Smart Land Management:
Insights from the Italian Co-Creation Workshop

#2

Climate-Resilient Orchard and Mountain Farming:
Insights from the Greek Co-Creation Workshop in Zagora

#3

Insights from the EARTHONE Online Workshop on Climate-Resilient Land Use

#4

A Framework to understand and tackle climate change impacts in Southern Europe

#5

Information Factory implementation and alignment on requirements for green data spaces

#6

Legal and regulatory requirements shaping climate smart land management

Practical guidance from EARTHONE's legal framework

EARTHONE podcast series

EARTHONE has launched its podcast series featuring perspectives from the project's pilot regions in Southern Europe, focusing on climate adaptation, land management and soil resilience under changing environmental conditions.

Episode 1 Soil Health and Living Labs	Episode 2 Climate Adaptation
<p>The first episode focuses on pilot experiences from Greece, Italy and North Macedonia, exploring how scientific knowledge, digital tools and local agricultural practices connect within EARTHONE's living labs.</p>	<p>The second episode continues the discussion with perspectives from Slovenia, Croatia and Spain, examining drought-prone regions, floodplain ecosystems, forestry, agroforestry and adaptive land-use strategies.</p>
<p>Listen to #01</p>	<p>Listen to #02</p>

Save the Date

EARTHONE will participate in [The Soils for Europe Conference 2026](#) as a co-organiser, with a project booth and a dedicated [World Café session](#) exploring how the socioeconomic impacts of climate change can be translated into effective policy responses. The session will create a space for dialogue between researchers,

practitioners and policymakers, focusing on practical pathways towards informed and inclusive climate action.

 Coimbra, Portugal

 7–11 September 2026

EARTHONE at events

EARTHONE partners contributed to several scientific and outreach events across Europe, connecting with researchers, students, agricultural stakeholders and the wider public.

Activities included:

- Agricultural Chemistry Winter School 2026 in Bologna, with contributions from DAFNAE – University of Padova
- Agrosience and Practice 2026 in North Macedonia, attended by Ag Futura Technologies
- Girls' Day 2026, organised by the University of Bremen team
- sCYence Fair 2026 and the EGU General Assembly 2026, featuring activities from the Cyprus Institute

The AgFutura team at Agrosience and Practice 2026

The Cyprus Institute team at the EGU 2026

AgroTech Hub webinar participation

In March, EARTHONE joined the AgroTech Hub Cluster webinar on Europe's agri-data ecosystem alongside several Horizon Europe projects working on digital agriculture and climate adaptation. The session explored how satellite, sensor and platform data can support decision-making across agriculture and land management.

[Watch the recording](#)

Sister projects' news

NEMESIS Opens Call for Additional Living Lab Sites

The Nemesis project is inviting applications to add additional experimental sites to their Living Labs to fight desertification and land degradation in the Mediterranean. Successful applicants should have access to an experimental site in the regions of

one of the Nemesis Living Labs (France, Spain, Italy, Cyprus, and Tunisia / Algeria) and will be actively contribute to soil health co-creation, testing, and demonstration activities within the respective Living Labs.

[Learn more and apply](#)

ENFORCE at CEMEPE 2026: SAVE THE DATE

The ENFORCE project will host a special session on July 14 during the 13th International Conference on Environmental Management, Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2026), taking place in Thessaloniki, Greece, from 12 to 16 July 2026.

The session will focus on environmental compliance, citizen science, Earth Observation and innovative approaches supporting environmental governance.

Join the MONALISA Community of Knowledge

The MONALISA [Community of Knowledge](#), led by ISPRA, connects researchers, policymakers and practitioners working to address land degradation and desertification across Europe and beyond. Members can take part in Annual Meetings, Café Talks, Open Calls for Young Researchers and other collaborative activities linked to the EU Mission Soil initiative.

To become a member, contact the team at monalisa_kc@isprambiente.it and [complete the form](#) to stay up to date with the latest news and opportunities from the Community.

New Podcast from LandShift

LandShift has launched the *Shifting LandScapes* podcast series with its first episode, *Entangled Landscapes: Research and Co-Creation in LandShift and AfroGrow*.

The episode explores how the Multi-Actor Approach supports collaboration, stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange across different land-use contexts.

[Listen now](#)

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